

APPLICATION OF MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTATION TO FIELD OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS WITH ENTERPRISE RISK MANAGEMENT AS A CASE STUDY

1 ABSTRACT

This contribution shows application of Computational Mathematics to Risk Management of an Business in an Economy. In particular it shows how Enterprise Risk Management can get benefitted by Computational Mathematics Approaches. Elementary Mathematics Linear Algebra also called Matrix Algebra along with elementary Mathematics Set Theory are used along with Python, NumPy and Pandas are used to show Applications of Computational Mathematics to Enterprise Risk Management of Business in Economy capturing four traits of Enterprise viz. Risk Impact, Risk Probability, Macro Economic Factors and Micro Economic Factors

2 INTRODUCTIONS

As mentioned in the title and abstract above it is about Enterprise Risk Management operating in Economy. First we take matrix representation of Risk represented in Impact and Row Matrix. Second Matrix captures Risk in the light of Micro and Macro factors. We slice the Risk-Impact-Probability to get significant entries. Similarly we slice the Risk-Micro-Macro Matrix to get the significant entries. Then perform operation on the resultant matrices to get final matrix comprising of Risk-Impact-Probability-Micro-Macro weightage as each cell of the Matrix. The Risk Management essentially is assigning the contingency and mitigation plan for each of the cells which would have already captured Risk factors on {Impact, probability, Micro, Macro}

	Likely Hood 0	Likely Hood 1	Likely Hood 2	Likely Hood 2
Impact 0	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j
Impact 1	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j
Impact 2	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j
Impact 2	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j	Probability Impact Weight Value PIW _j

	Micro 0	Micro 1	Micro 2	Micro 3
Macro 0	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i
Macro 1	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i
Macro 2	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i
Macro 3	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i	Economic Weight E _i

	PIW _j	PIW _j	PIW _j	PIW _j
EW _i	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}
EW _i	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}
EW _i	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}
EW _i	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}	EPIW _{ij}

Figure 1 Is Impact Probability Micro and Macro Captured in the figure. Resultant Matrix combing ERM factors

3 OBJECTIVE

As explained in Introduction

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 CONCEPTS OF MATHEMATICS, LINEAR ALGEBRA, SET THEORY USAGE OF ERM

Set Theory: Set A essentially comprises of individual entities $\{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, \dots, a_n\}$

Mathematically Set A is $\{a_i\} : 0 < i < n$

Matrix: Matrix is two dimensional representation which essentially will have important Row and also Column. So each cell of Matrix is unique combination of Row Characteristics and column characteristics. Please note row is leading attribute. One should represent ones data bearing this in mind.

Matrix is $\{a_{ij}\} : 0 < i < n \text{ and } 0 < j < m$

When one is interested in let us say slicing operation with particular interest in resultant **sub-matrix where $i > n_1$ and $j > m_1$**

Matrix is $\{a_{ij}\} : n_1 < i < n \text{ and } m_1 < j < m$

3.2 PROMPT ENGINEERING TO RETRIEVE PYTHON BASED PANDAS AND NUMPY CODE SNIPPETS via COPILOT.MICROSOFT.COM INTERACTING WITH CHATGPT LLM

3.2.1 Give me syntax in python for Panda frame creation. Followed by slicing.

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
# Creating a DataFrame
```

```
data = {  
    'Name': ['Alice', 'Bob', 'Charlie', 'David', 'Eva'],  
    'Age': [25, 30, 35, 40, 45],  
    'City': ['New York', 'Los Angeles', 'Chicago', 'Houston', 'Phoenix']  
}
```

```
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
```

```
# Display the DataFrame
```

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```
print("DataFrame:")
```

```
print(df)
```

```
# Slicing the DataFrame
```

```
# Example 1: Slicing rows by index
```

```
sliced_df_rows = df[1:4]
```

```
# Example 2: Slicing columns by column names
```

```
sliced_df_columns = df[['Name', 'City']]
```

```
# Example 3: Slicing both rows and columns
```

```
sliced_df_both = df.loc[1:3, ['Name', 'City']]
```

```
print("\nSliced DataFrame (rows):")
```

```
print(sliced_df_rows)
```

```
print("\nSliced DataFrame (columns):")
```

```
print(sliced_df_columns)
```

```
print("\nSliced DataFrame (both rows and columns):")
```

```
print(sliced_df_both)
```

3.2.2 Give me python syntax for slicing a panda frame to get matrix beyond a row and a column value

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
# Sample DataFrame
```

```
data = {
```

```
    'A': [1, 2, 3, 4],
```

```
    'B': [5, 6, 7, 8],
```

```
    'C': [9, 10, 11, 12],
```

```
    'D': [13, 14, 15, 16]
```

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```
}
```

```
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
```

```
# Specify the starting row and column
```

```
start_row = 1
```

```
start_col = 2
```

```
# Slicing the DataFrame to get the matrix beyond the specified row and column
```

```
sliced_matrix = df.iloc[start_row:, start_col:]
```

```
print("Original DataFrame:")
```

```
print(df)
```

```
print("\nSliced Matrix:")
```

```
print(sliced_matrix)
```

3.2.3 Now Numpy APIs Syntax. Give me Python code to convert given matrix into row and column Arrays without using matrix.shape

```
import numpy as np
```

```
# Given matrix
```

```
matrix = np.array([
```

```
    [1, 2, 3],
```

```
    [4, 5, 6],
```

```
    [7, 8, 9]
```

```
])
```

```
# Convert matrix to row arrays
```

```
rows = [row for row in matrix]
```

```
# Convert matrix to column arrays
```

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```
columns = [col for col in matrix.T] # Transposing the matrix to iterate columns
```

```
print("Original Matrix:")
```

```
print(matrix)
```

```
print("\nRow Arrays:")
```

```
for row in rows:
```

```
    print(row)
```

```
print("\nColumn Arrays:")
```

```
for col in columns:
```

```
    print(col)
```

3.2.4 Now give me NumPy to convert given matrix into single dimensional Array

```
import numpy as np
```

```
# Given matrix
```

```
matrix = np.array([
```

```
    [1, 2, 3],
```

```
    [4, 5, 6],
```

```
    [7, 8, 9]
```

```
])
```

```
# Convert matrix to single-dimensional array
```

```
single_dim_array = matrix.flatten()
```

```
print("Original Matrix:")
```

```
print(matrix)
```

```
print("\nSingle-Dimensional Array:")
```

```
print(single_dim_array)
```

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3.2.5 Now give me NumPy to create matrix $N \times M$ from two single dimensional Arrays of dimensions N and M respectively without using `numpy.axis`

```
import numpy as np

# Two single-dimensional arrays
array1 = np.array([1, 2, 3]) # Example array of dimension N
array2 = np.array([4, 5, 6, 7]) # Example array of dimension M

# Creating an N x M matrix
matrix = np.outer(array1, array2)

print("Array 1 (N):")
print(array1)

print("Array 2 (M):")
print(array2)

print("\nN x M Matrix:")
print(matrix)
```

3.3 APPLICATION OF CONCEPTS OF COMPUTATIONAL MATHEMATICS TO ERM: WORKING PROGRAM FOR ERM

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd

# Comeup with Impact_Probability_Matrix from given data frame

#Row is impact and column is probability

Impapact_probability_matrix = {
    'Probability_0': [4, 5, 6,7],
```

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```
'Probability_1': [7, 8, 9,10],
'Probability_2': [10, 11, 12,13],
'Probability_3': [10, 11, 12,13]
}

# Creating Datafarme from given dictionary
df = pd.DataFrame(Impapact_probability_matrix)

#Display the DataFrame
print('DataFrame with row as impact and column as prabability for risk caharacteristics
of Business')

print(df)

#Converting the DataFrame to a NumPy Matrix
data_frame_to_matrix = df.to_numpy()

#Sub Matrix starting from 2nd row and 2nd column
#For the time being hard code it to 2. Hard coding is not best software practice. Here
focus is demonstration
starting_row_column_value = 2

#Sliced Impact_likelihood_matrix containing high impact and high probability values

sliced_impact_probability_matrix =
data_frame_to_matrix[starting_row_column_value:.,starting_row_column_value:]

print('Sliced or reduced version of Risk-Impact-Probability Matrix of Business:')
print(sliced_impact_probability_matrix)

#Come up with Macro and Micro Economic representation of business environment
#Each row is micro and column is macro
```

```
#Intentionally retain the exact same values as in first data frame.
# Because final values are easy to verify after the process
Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros = {
    'given_macro_0':[4, 5, 6,7],
    'given_macro_1': [7, 8, 9,10],
    'given_macro_2': [10, 11, 12,13],
    'given_macro_3': [10, 11, 12,13]
}

# Creating Impact_Weight_Matric
df = pd.DataFrame(Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros)
#Display the DataFrame
print("DataFrame with row as micro factor and column as macro factor for risk
caharacteristics of Business:")
print(df)

#Converting the DataFrame to a NumPy Matrix
data_frame_to_matrix = df.to_numpy()

#Sub Matrix starting from 2nd row and 2nd column
#For the time being hard code it to 2. Hard coding is not best software practice. Here
focus is demonstration
starting_row_column_value = 2

sliced_Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros_macro =
data_frame_to_matrix[starting_row_column_value:,starting_row_column_value:]
print('Sliced or reduced version of Risk-MicroMacro-Businessix Matrix of Business:')
print(sliced_Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros_macro)
```

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```
#Convert sliced impact_probability matrix into vector using flatten
```

```
sliced_impact_probability_vector = sliced_impact_probability_matrix.flatten()
```

```
#Convert sliced_Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros_macro using  
flatten
```

```
sliced_Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros_macro_vector =  
sliced_Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros_macro.flatten()
```

```
#We converted the sliced_impact_probability_matrix to 1D array and  
sliced_Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros_macro to 1D array
```

```
#Now come up with Matrix of Impact_Probability_Matrix *  
Economic_Business_Environment_for_various_micros
```

```
final_impact_probability_micro_macro_matrix =  
np.outer(sliced_impact_probability_vector,sliced_Economic_Business_Environment_fo  
r_various_micros_macro_vector)
```

```
print('Final Matrix comprising of Risk Impact, Risk Probability Micro and Macro of  
Business for Decision makers to assign contingency and mitigation plans')
```

```
print(final_impact_probability_micro_macro_matrix)
```

```
#If needed it can be sliced further. But we should NOT do that
```

4 OBSERVATIONS AND INFERENCE

DataFrame with row as impact and column as probability for risk characteristics of Business

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	Probability_0	Probability_1	Probability_2	Probability_3
0	4	7	10	10
1	5	8	11	11
2	6	9	12	12
3	7	10	13	13

Sliced or reduced version of Risk-Impact-Probability Matrix of Business:

[[12 12]

[13 13]]

DataFrame with row as micro factor and column as macro factor for risk characteristics of Business:

	given_macro_0	given_macro_1	given_macro_2	given_macro_3
0	4	7	10	10
1	5	8	11	11
2	6	9	12	12
3	7	10	13	13

Sliced or reduced version of Risk-MicroMacro-Businessix Matrix of Business:

[[12 12]

[13 13]]

Final Matrix comprising of Risk Impact, Risk Probability Micro and Macro of Business for Decision makers to assign contingency and mitigation plans

[[144 144 156 156]

[144 144 156 156]

[156 156 169 169]

[156 156 169 169]]

Not all Risk characteristics comprising of { Impact, Probability, Micro, Macro} have same weight. Depending upon the situation final Matrix will have different weight for each of the situations captured as individual cell of the Matrix. Therefore, Unique Contingency and Mitigation plan for each unique situation or cell of the Matrix.

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Slicing of Matrix or Reduced Matrix Approach may not be appreciated in first look but 10 X 10 Matrix is very much a reality. If Slicing is not performed, the resulting Matrix will be large. From Business decision making for each unique Risk becomes daunting and whole process becomes diluted. Diluted process will not achieve what was intended.

5 FUTURE KNOWLEDGE PATH

This Article can be a great feed-back for Enterprise Framework such as ERM-COSO-2023 framework. The Coso.org will be approached to know if they are interested in incorporating the improvements suggested via this Article. As of now Coso.org is the first avenue for improvement in ERM-Coso-2023 Framework. Subsequently other ERM frameworks will also be approached for existing ERM frameworks improvements.

6 REFERENCES

1. <https://abhinandanhpatil.net>
2. <https://coso.org>